

Anonymized student prog. env.

Survey Flow

Standard: Consent block (1 Question)

Branch: New Branch

If

If We are asking you to be a volunteer in this research study. To participate, you must be a college student pursuing a computing degree at <university>, 18 years or older, and located in the US... Disagree Is Selected

EndSurvey: Advanced

Block: Programming environments (22 Questions)

Standard: Background (10 Questions)

EndSurvey: Advanced

Page Break

Start of Block: Consent block

Q1.1 We are asking you to be a volunteer in this research study. To participate, you must be a college student pursuing a computing degree at <university>, 18 years or older, and located in the US when completing the survey. This survey is a collaboration between <universities> to see how students use and learn about programming environments, such as Visual Studio Code, Git, Docker, Poetry, IntelliJ, Eclipse, NetBeans, Jupyter Notebooks, and others. Since we are interested in your experience with programming environments, there are no right or wrong answers in this survey. It should take no longer than 5 minutes to complete. The risks involved are no greater than those involved in daily activities. Please note that you will not directly benefit from participating in this study. However, <ineyour course instructor may offer extra credit (less than 1% of the total course grade) for completing the survey, which will provide a certificate of completion for your records upon completion. If extra credit is offered for the survey, your instructor will also provide a non-research alternative if you are unable to or choose not to participate. We will comply with any applicable laws and regulations regarding confidentiality, and the data from this survey will be aggregated to protect your privacy. If you have any questions about the study, you may contact <research team>. If you have any questions about your rights as a research participant, you may contact the <university IRB>.

By selecting "Agree" below, it means that you have read the information given in this consent form, and you would like to participate in this survey.

- Agree
- Disagree

End of Block: Consent block

Start of Block: Programming environments

Q2.1

What do you consider as part of a programming environment? Select all that apply.

- Integrated development environments
 - Text editors
 - Version control systems
 - Package or dependency managers
 - Operating systems
 - Workflow tools
 - Device hardware
 - Virtualization tools
 - Other: _____
-

Q2.2

How knowledgeable do you think you are with programming environments compared with your peers?

- 0
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - 10
-

Q2.3

Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments.

	Currently use or used before	Heard of but not used	Not sure what it is
Android Studio	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
BlueJ	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Docker	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Git	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gradle	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IntelliJ	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jupyter Notebook	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
npm	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
pip	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sublime Text	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
VS Code	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Xcode	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q2.4 How did you learn about these tools? Select all that apply.

- Friends or family
 - Bootcamps
 - High-school
 - Online sources (eg., MOOCs, YouTube, Online guides)
 - Computing clubs
 - College courses (in-person, online, or hybrid)
 - Hackathons
 - Internship, co-op, or previous work experience
 - Personal projects
 - Other: _____
-

Q2.5

What is your preferred option for learning about programming environments and how to use them? Select all that apply.

- Formal learning environment (e.g., classroom or as part of a class)
- Informal learning environment (e.g., club or hackathon)
- On my own or as part of my work (e.g., personal project, internship, or position at an organization)
- Other: _____

Q2.6 How has your experience with programming environments been?

- Extremely easy
- Somewhat easy
- Neither easy nor difficult
- Somewhat difficult
- Extremely difficult

Page Break

Q2.7

Have you faced any of the following difficulties with programming environments (for example, VS Code, Git, Conda, IntelliJ, etc.)? Select all that apply.

- Installing the environment
 - Confusion with the UI
 - Knowing when to use the right environment
 - Managing dependencies or versions of a project or language
 - Running programs with the environment
 - Learning certain features of the environment
 - Setting up the environment for a project
 - Other: _____
-

Q2.8

When using a programming environment **for a class** where do you go for help when facing issues with the tool? Select all that apply.

- Office hours
 - Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
 - Friends
 - Co-workers
 - AI tools
 - Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
 - Other: _____
-

Q2.9 When using a programming environment **outside of a class**, where do you go for help when facing issues with the tool? Select all that apply.

- Office hours
 - Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
 - Friends
 - Co-workers
 - AI tools
 - Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
 - Other: _____
-

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = npm [Currently use or used before]

Q2.10 If you encounter an issue with npm, such as missing peer dependencies, build failures, or version conflicts, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = VS Code [Currently use or used before]

Q2.11 If you encounter an issue with VS Code, such as problems installing an extension, settings not saving, or problems with the terminal, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = IntelliJ [Currently use or used before]

Q2.12 If you encounter an issue with IntelliJ, such as failing to load a class, missing libraries, or problems with the debugger, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = Gradle [Currently use or used before]

Q2.13 If you encounter an issue with Gradle, such as a missing plugin error, dependency resolution failures, or build script issues, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = Git [Currently use or used before]

Q2.14 When using Git, where are you most likely to go for help if you accidentally delete a commit / branch, or encounter issues with pushing or merging?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = Android Studio [Currently use or used before]

Q2.15 If you encounter an issue with Android Studio, such as a build error when compiling an Android application or issues running the emulator, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = pip [Currently use or used before]

Q2.16 If you encounter an issue with pip, such as trying to install a package, resolve dependencies, or upgrade a package, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = Docker [Currently use or used before]

Q2.17 If you encounter an error in Docker when trying to run a container, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = Xcode [Currently use or used before]

Q2.18 If you encounter an issue in Xcode, such as build errors or problems with running an iOS application, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Display this question:

If Select which option best describes your use of the following programming environments. = Jupyter Notebook [Currently use or used before]

Q2.19 If you encounter an issue in Jupyter Notebook, such as problems with running cells or missing packages, where are you most likely to go for help?

- I already know how to fix this
- Office hours
- Class forums (e.g., Piazza, Ed Discussion)
- AI tools
- Online sources (e.g., Google, StackOverflow)
- Friends
- Co-workers
- Other: _____

Page Break

Q2.20 Which of the following is most applicable to you when choosing a programming environment? (Optional)

- I use the tools that the project, job, or class provides
 - I have one environment that I use for everything regardless of the project
 - I mostly use one environment but otherwise use what the project provides
 - I use multiple environments for different purposes
 - Other: _____
-

Q2.21 Why do you choose one (or multiple) programming environment(s) over others? (Optional)

Q2.22 Select which statement best describes your feelings or experience towards the following programming environments. (Optional)

	I have heard about or used this tool before		I would like to learn more about this tool	
	Yes	No or unsure	Yes	No or don't care

Zed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
yarn	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Spyder	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
WSL	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Codespaces	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Thonny	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Google Colab	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Processing IDE	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
maven	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
NetBeans	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vim	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Programming environments

Start of Block: Background

Q3.1 What is your major?

- Computer Science
 - Information Technology
 - Computational Science
 - Computer Engineering
 - Data Science
 - Related to Computer Science
 - Used to be in a computing related field but left the major
 - Other: _____
-

Q3.2 What year of college are you in?

- First-year
 - Second-year
 - Third-year
 - Fourth-year and above
 - Master's student
 - PhD student
-

Q3.3 What classes have you taken or are currently taking? Select all that apply. (Anonymized for submission: This question listed 10 core classes in our computing program.)

- Anonymized core class
 - Anonymized core class
-

Q3.4 What is your age?

- 18-24
 - 25-34
 - 35-44
 - 45-54
 - 55-64
 - 65-74
 - 75 or older
 - I prefer not to answer
-

Q3.5 Have you participated in any of the following extracurricular activities related to computing? Select all that apply.

- Bootcamps
 - Computing clubs
 - Hackathons
 - Personal projects
 - Research
 - Internships or co-ops
 - Part-time or full-time position related to computing
 - Other: _____
-

Q3.6 Is English your first language, or did you use it as your primary language during your K-12 education?

Yes

No

Q3.7 How would you describe your disability / ability status? (Optional)

A cognitive disability

A learning disability

A mobility impairment or physical disability

A sensory impairment (e.g., vision, hearing)

A sensory processing or integration disorder

A disability or impairment not listed here. Please specify:

Prefer to self-describe:

I do not identify with a disability or impairment

I prefer not to say

Q3.8 What is your nationality? (Optional)

▼ Afghan ... Zimbabwean

Q3.9 How do you currently describe yourself? (Optional)

- Male
 - Female
 - Genderfluid
 - Transgender
 - Two-spirit
 - Non-binary
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe:
-

Q3.10 Which best describes your race / ethnicity? (Optional)

- American Indian, Alaska native or First Nations
 - Asian
 - Black or African-American
 - Hispanic or Latino / Latina or Latin American
 - Middle Eastern or North African
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
 - White
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe:
-

End of Block: Background
